

Implementation of Memory based FFT Processor for high data rates

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ABSTRACT:

Digital systems, especially communication systems, make extensive use of FFT. Processing blocks like fast Fourier transform (FFT) account for the bulk of these systems' hardware complexity. Communication systems are increasingly demanding faster data speeds, necessitating high-point fast Fourier transforms (1024/2048/4096, etc.). The CORDIC method is used by the FFT processor to do complex multiplications. If you want to learn how the butterfly unit works but don't want to use a multiplier, the CORDIC unit is a great alternative. Because it uses just addition and shift operations,

the CORDIC unit is hardware efficient and may be used for FFT's butterfly unit calculations. A low-latency, area-efficient, and power-efficient system is being implemented as part of this project. For decimation in time (DIT) with 16 points and 32 points, the radix-2 and radix-4 butterfly units are used, respectively. This article discusses the radix-2 method with respect to unsigned, signed, and complex numbers.

Index terms: FFT Processor, Memory based, Real value data, CORDIC (Coordinate Rotation Digital Computer)

I. INTRODUCTION

Many applications rely on field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), including fast Fourier transform (FFT) processors used in signal and image processing. High throughput is one of its many features, thus we may use it to

may use the FPGA chip to do high-speed calculations in real-time.

The CORDIC approach is used in this implemented article to handle complex multiplications in the 32-bit high performance FFT algorithm radix-4. Computing FFTs is made easier by its speed. An successful approach for fast Fourier transform (FFT) processors, the radix-2 algorithm displays results using the butterfly unit. There are a lot

of complicated multiplications in the butterfly unit. The 32-point butterfly unit will be more complicated, and they would be deduced using the radix-4 FFT technique. A decrease in latency, a reduction in power consumption, and a reduction in hardware complexity are all results of the fundamental enhancements made to FFT designs. There are two main kinds of FFT architectures: memory-based and pipelined. A processing element (PE) made up of a butterfly unit, data memory units, and control units is included in memory-based designs that are associated with fast Fourier transforms (FFTs).

II. FFT Algorithm:

FFT Algorithm:

FFT is mainly used to reduce more number of computations in discrete Fourier Transform. The Fast Fourier Transform is mostly used in digital signal processing (DSP) i.e., spectral analysis, filtering etc. there are different applications such as audio, radar, speech, image processing and biomedical signal processing are the applications for FFT. In this paper the input

is taken as floating point number. The FFT can be compute using two methods: DIT and DIF, In DIT-FFT method we change the data from bit reversal order to normal order and in DIF-FFT we take its converse. The computation of FFT using DIT method is easy as compare to DIF method. By using this radix-2 and radix-4 FFT algorithms we can design FFT Processor. In this paper we used the radix-4 FFT algorithm. The radix-4 FFT algorithm divides the N-point FFT into small parts until 2-point FFT is obtained. This FFT algorithm splits the N point FFT into four point FFT and it is referred as radix-4 algorithm. The FFT processor have very fast execution speed and low power consumption when it is used in wireless communication systems.

Radix-4 FFT Algorithm:

The N point DFT is defined as

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x(n) W_N^{nk}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$$

$$\text{where, } W_N^{nk} = e^{-j(2\pi/N)nk}$$

The radix-4 DIT FFT is explained in the following expressions. The N point input is decimated into 4 subparts namely, $x(4m)$, $x(4m+1)$, $x(4m+2)$, $x(4m+3)$,

where $k = 0, 1, \dots, N/4-1$.

Discrete fourier transform of radix-4 in DIT FFT can be given as:

$$X(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m) W_N^{4mk} + \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+1) W_N^{(4m+1)k} + \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+2) W_N^{(4m+2)k} + \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+3) W_N^{(4m+3)k}$$

Let $W_N^{4mk} = W_{N/4}^{mk}$, $W_N^k = W^p$,

$$A = \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m) W_{N/4}^{mk},$$

$$B = \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+1) W_N^{(4m+1)k}$$

$$C = \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+2) W_N^{(4m+2)k}$$

$$D = \sum_{m=0}^{N/4-1} x(4m+3) W_N^{(4m+3)k}$$

$$X(k) = A + BW^p + CW^{2p} + DW^{3p}$$

$$X(k + N/4) = A - j.BW^p - CW^{2p} + j.DW^{3p}$$

$$X(k + N/2) = A - BW^p + CW^{2p} - DW^{3p}$$

$$X(k + 3N/4) = A + BW^p - CW^{2p} - j.DW^{3p}$$

The above equations are arranged in a matrix form, according to the limitations of W_N^{nk}

$$\begin{bmatrix} A' \\ B' \\ C' \\ D' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -j & -1 & j \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & j & -1 & -j \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} A \\ BW^p \\ CW^{2p} \\ DW^{3p} \end{bmatrix} = Q \cdot \begin{bmatrix} A \\ BW^p \\ CW^{2p} \\ DW^{3p} \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$A' = X(k), B' = X(k + N/4), C' = X(k + N/2), D' = X(k + 3N/4)$$

So, a radix-4 FFT butterfly unit computations are referred as sequences of the input and initially rotating factor will multiply the inputs, the Q matrix will be left, that is the total multiplications from the radix-4 fast fourier transform will be lesser than the radix-2 fast fourier transform.

III. IMPLEMENTED SYSTEM

FFT is a mostly used algorithm for complexity reduction of the computations, the computations of FFT speed should be high for the high data rate. Hence, in the future base stations that supports multimode, the FFT processor need to support different DFTs and FFTs.

Different architectures are there to support the high data rates for processing of FFT. Single path delay feedback(SDF), Multipath delay feedback(MDF) and Memory based architectures support diverse non-power-of two point DFT's.

The throughput of single path delay feedback architecture has 1 x Clock rate that is restricted for that level and that will be difficult to reach requirement that is 1.

The MDF architecture supports one 1536

DFT size only, and the range that supports for the

size of DFT and its extended is

= X(k + 3N/4) difficult. So, this implemented processor is modified and optimized based on the

architecture which has radix-r general process of the butterfly unit and this will be easy to support the different radices and reutilizing the hardware.

A single processing element is used to accomplish the Radix-r butterfly operation. The core memory block stores the data, intermediate outcomes, and twiddle factor. Using bit-reverse to reorganise data is another possible use. You need N memory words to do N -point FFT. This design had low-throughput, high-latency, and needed less expensive technology. It is possible to decrease the clock rate by using a high-radix processing device, however doing so adds complexity. The number of operations required to calculate the FFT is $(N/2) \log_2 N$, and it is done consecutively. The fundamental architecture is the memory-based one, which includes the radix-r generic butterfly unit. In order to enhance the architecture and achieve varied DFT or FFT sizes with high data rates and reduce hardware cost, the memory based architecture is altered and optimised.

With 32 bits fed into data memory and a 32-point butterfly unit with radix-4, the built system uses a memory-based fast Fourier transform (FFT) processor to execute various operations in order to decrease the

details on the implemented FFT Processor's memory use, power consumption, and latency

Fig. 1 shows that the implemented FFT processor is given by

- 1) The data memory consists of two memory groups, they are Memory group 1 and Memory group 2
- 2) A block floating point memory is used for the exponents of the given information storing in BFP format.
- 3) The PE consists of a Twiddle factor based CORDIC unit, a FFT Controller, a Reconfigurable butterfly unit, and a W_LUT.

Fig.1: Structure of the Implemented System FFT Processor

In this paper, a radix-4 based 32-point FFT processor is designed by using the CORDIC unit. The processor which is implemented and designed in the format of FPGA and this FPGA characteristics of low cost, effective and high data rates. The CORDIC algorithm for the implementation of the butterfly operations of the FFT computations which is excluded for the use of storing the twiddle factors and angles and these will save lot of hardware compared to remaining techniques.

Block floating point (BFP):

BFP is a technique that is employed for a mathematical approach for the floating point. This method will allocate a full data block like an exponent, instead of single data itself and these will be allocated to an exponent, so by aligning them as a set of data means block, instead of basic floating point.

The operations of BFP algorithm would be done by a set of data i.e., block using a same exponent, it will be useful limit for the space utilization within the architecture to perform similar functions as BFP algorithms.

Twiddle Factor based CORDIC unit: CORDIC (coordinate rotation digital computer), which is a hardware effective repetitive method for trigonometric function

computations and additions, multiplications and data type conversions. It is a basic and efficient algorithm for the trigonometric functional computations, exponentials and logarithms with the base, with one digit or digit - to - digit per iteration. CORDIC algorithm is also referred as digit-by-digit algorithms. The Discrete Fourier Transform has complex multiplications which is N^2 and complex additions which is $N(N-1)$. Except the twiddle factors, $O(n^2)$ is for the complexity of computations in DFT. Including the twiddle factors, $N \log_2 N$ is for the complexity of computations.

To reduce the number of computations from the calculations of DFT and IDFT the twiddle factor is used.

Rotating vector quantity is also referred as a twiddle factor. Therefore, it gives a N bit DFT or IDFT computations, this observes that twiddle factor values will be iterative for every point of N cycles. The similar block of data at each and every $(N-1)^{\text{th}}$ cycle does the calculations a little bit simpler. The step $(N-1)$ is the first sequence, we could alternatively tell that twiddle factor also has two properties those are periodicity/a cyclic property.

Fig.2 Rotation mode CORDIC unit

Rotation-Mode Reconfigurable
CORDIC

Rotation mode reconfigurable CORDIC method is used in the implemented system and it is as shown in fig.3 and it is consisting of three blocks

- 1) Preprocessing unit
- 2) Reconfigurable CORDIC rotation unit
- 3) Post processing unit.

The first block preprocessing unit makes sure that the input of the angle of rotation to the structure of CORDIC processing and this structure will be in the range $(0, \pi/4)$ and the angle of rotation which is maximum and it is handled by micro rotation sequence generator is represented by $\pi/4$. The last block represents post processing unit which requires for the different circular trajectory for the process of swapping/complement of trigonometric sine/cosine data and it depends upon the octant rotation angle which is shown in the fig. For controlling trajectories for reconfigurable CORDIC the

user has to change a 1bit of the signal referred as T. The reconfigurable rotation mode CORDIC has the rotation matrix and it will obtain after unifying the rotation matrices of hyperbolic and circular trajectories. The given equations are the rotation matrices

$$R_{ct} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 2^{-(2s_i+1)} & -(2^{-s_i} - 2^{-(3s_i+3)}) \\ 2^{-s_i} - 2^{-(3s_i+3)} & 1 - 2^{-(2s_i+1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_{hi} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + 2^{-(2s_i+1)} & 2^{-s_i} + 2^{-(3s_i+2)} \\ 2^{-s_i} + 2^{-(3s_i+2)} & 1 + 2^{-(2s_i+1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \pm 2^{-(2s_i+1)} & \pm(2^{-s_i} \pm 2^{-(3s_i+2+T)}) \\ 2^{-s_i} \pm 2^{-(3s_i+2+T)} & 1 \pm 2^{-(2s_i+1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$T = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for hyperbolic} \\ 1 & \text{for circular.} \end{cases}$$

This Twiddle Factor based CORDIC unit is to perform the CORDIC unit operations and also aligning operations. In this unit, it performs the rotate, shift, aligned operations and it will be easy to encode the data.

FFT Controller:

A control unit typically operates the fast fourier transform (FFT) processor, and the FFT processor's circuit relies on input from an external unit. Here, the output signal is dependent on the value of the next state and is based on an optimised and modified Moore state technique. A signal that is regulated by a design is known as "CLK," and the design functions are referred to by a design. With regard to the controller's inputs

In order to reset this FFT processor, there is an input

signal called "RST." Additionally, the processor has an input buffer that stores data for the following stage. This FFT controller will have an input signal called "EN" that controls the processor's enable state transition. The output signal is enabled by the presence of a "SYNC_OUT" signal.

This FFT controller takes data from a Twiddle factor-based CORDIC unit and sends it in a stage-by-stage manner that is proportional to the data's length. This part analyses the input, which includes both the real and imaginary values, and uses this information to drive the FFT algorithm. To clarify, the FFT algorithm retrieves data from the memory bank and writes it back.

Reconfigurable Butterfly unit:

The components of the Reconfigurable Butterfly Unit include With four inputs and four outputs, this is the butterfly unit of a radix-4 algorithm that takes 32 points as inputs. With M being the number of stages, the FFT size is $4M$. A radix-2 substage is included in one stage. An N -bit Discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is divided into four $N/4$ point DFTs, sixteen $N/16$ point DFTs,

and so on using the radix-4 DIF FFT.

The radix-2 FFT method employs DIF FFT, where the DFT equation is expressed as the product of two equations. A half of the input sequence requires one calculation for the first half and another for the second half. Just as the radix-4 DIF fast Fourier transform (FFT) split the DFT equation into four parts, each of which is subsequently divided into four equations, the fourth sample's outputs are computed in this way.

Fig.3: Basic butterfly computation in a radix-4 FFT algorithm.

The equations of radix-4 DIT is illustrated in section-II. There are two different types of algorithms, they are DIT and DIF which is Decimation in time and Decimation in frequency.

Fig 4. Butterfly unit of 32-point Radix 4 DIT FFT implementation

Butterfly unit performs the FFT algorithm which is reconfigurable. From FFT controller, this unit will get the data and this data will be signed/real values/imaginary value format. In this butterfly unit, the data will be added and multiplied and then the output data will supply to W_LUT unit **W_LUT:** By using this W_LUT block, we convert the data and write/store the data and sends the data to memory. In this it will re-sequence the data and it collects the data from address and sends the data to output.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this implemented method, we are giving 32bits of input to the processor and will compute using 32 point FFT with radix 4 to the Implemented memory based FFT Processor. By using this approach, the area will be reduced, less delay and low memory usage will be there. The RTL schematic and the simulation results are shown below. All the designs are simulated using by using Xilinx ISE 14.7 tool.

Results:

	FFT Size	Radix	LUT(s)	Delay(ns)	Power Consumption(W)
Implementation Method	16	2	523	4.360ns	1.098
Implementation Method	32	4	1,415	3.820ns	1.138

RTL SCHEMATIC:

V. CONCLUSION:

For image and digital signal processing, we built a memory-based fast-forward FFT processor that can handle up to 1024-point FFTs with ease. A 32-point radix-4 FFT technique is used to decrease complexity and the number of calculations, while reusing hardware resources reduces the cost of the hardware. For hardware-efficient support of FFTs and DFTs, a CORDIC method is used. The processor's latency, power consumption, and memory storage may all be improved with the use of a memory-based design. The findings of the simulations and synthesis have been validated using the Xilinx ISE 14.7 tool.

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